

DOM AFONSO MARIA UNGARELLI: A BISHOP OF MARANHÃO IN THE VATICAN COUNCIL II

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7178514

Laersio da Silva Machado

Priest of the Diocese of Empress. Bachelor in Theology from the Institute of Higher Studies of Maranhão – IESMA (São Luís/MA, 2012). Student of the Ecclesiastical Master's Degree in Canon Law at the São Paulo Apostle Faculty of Canon Law (São Paulo/SP).

E-mail: padre.laersio@outlook.com. ORCID: <http://orcid.org/0000-0001-7814-837X>.

Summary

Vatican II was the first Council to count on the presence of the bishops of Maranhão. Dom Afonso Maria Ungarelli, MSC (1897-1988), prelate bishop of Pinheiro (1946-1975), stood out as one of the Maranhão Council Fathers with a great contribution, both in the ante-preparatory phase, with the most extensive "votum" of the bishops of the Ecclesiastical Province, as well as in the subsequent phases, being a consultant to the Preparatory Commission for the Discipline of the Sacraments and, during the Conciliar Sessions, a member of the "De Missionibus" Commission and the second bishop of Maranhão with more interventions in the debates in the Conciliar Class. This article aims to analyze the participation of Dom Ungarelli from the texts of his suggestions and interventions compiled in the Synod Acts. The historical path and pastoral situation of the Prelature of Pinheiro in the period when the Council was held are briefly outlined. In general terms, the prosopography of Dom Ungarelli is presented and the texts of his contributions in the different phases of the Second Vatican Council are analyzed, among which one was accepted by the Council Fathers in the Decree "Ad Gentes" on the missionary activity of the Catholic Church. Church (n. 6, note 37).

Keywords: Second Vatican Ecumenical Council. Conciliar Fathers. Maranhão. Alfonso Maria Ungarelli.

INTRODUCTION

This article is the result of a broader research ⁷, inserted in the perspective of the study of the Council from the Council Fathers, investigating the role of the Maranhão episcopate in the different phases of Vatican II. In order to do so, we analyze the participation of the bishops

⁷cf. MACHADO, 2012. Completion of course work for the Bachelor's Degree in Theology at the Institute of Higher Studies of Maranhão – IESMA, in São Luís Maranhão, under the guidance of Prof. Me. Foot. Umberto Guidotti, *in memoriam* (born 1941, died on October 11, 2021, in Pistoia, Italy, on the day in which Saint John XXIII opened the Second Vatican Council).

of the Ecclesiastical Province of São Luís do Maranhão in the Second Vatican Council from the texts of their contributions compiled in the Synod Acts⁸. In the clipping presented here, we analyze the performance of Dom Affonso Maria Ungarelli, MSC, bishop of the Prelature *nullius* de Pinheiro, in the different phases of the Council.

Initially, we seek to outline the scenario of the Prelature of Pinheiro in the period between the announcement and the solemn conclusion of the Council. Next, the profile of this Father Conciliar from Maranhão is presented, in a prosopography essay. The inventory of their contributions in the preparatory phase and in the Conciliar Class is then analyzed.

1 THE *PRELAZIA NULLIUS* DE PINHEIRO ON THE THRESHOLD OF THE COUNCIL

The West Coast and part of the Baixada Maranhense are among the regions of the state with the oldest presence of colonizers and the Church. Alcântara, Guimarães, São Bento and Pinheiro became parishes of the Diocese of São Luís do Maranhão between the 18th and 19th centuries (cf. MARQUES, 2008, p. 92-93, 590, 795 and 839). The area corresponding to these parishes and the others on the Western Coast, Baixada Maranhense and the Gurupi region were entirely under the jurisdiction of the Archdiocese of São Luís do Maranhão until 1922, when the Prelature *nullius* de São José de Grajaú was created, which covered the municipality of Turiaçu.

According to Frei Metódio de Nembro (1955, p. 103), since “1925 there was already talk of the creation of two prelatures in Gurupí [sic], one covering the border zone with Pará, and the other comprising the northeast region⁹ [sic] from Maranhão”. On the same date that he created the Diocese of Caxias – July 22, 1939 – Pope Pius XI created the Prelature *nullius de Pinheiro* by the bull *Ad Maius Christifidelium*, placing it in the care of the Congregation of Missionaries of the Sacred Heart of Jesus (cf. AAS 32, 1940, pp. 112-113).

When the *Decretum Executionis* of the Apostolic Constitution was published by the Nunciature in Brazil, in 1940, “the war was already raging on the European 'fronts' and in the Atlantic Ocean”, which made it impossible for the Italian Missionaries of the Sacred Heart to

⁸Published under the titles “*Acta et documenta Concilio Oecumenico Vaticano II apparando*” (hereinafter referred to as ADA) and “*Acta synodalia sacrosancti Concilii Oecumenici Vaticani II*” (hereinafter referred to as AS) by the Vatican Polyglot Typography, currently available on the internet on the website of the Faculty of Canon Law of the Pontifical Gregorian University, Rome: <<https://www.iuscangreg.it/acta.php>>.

⁹The Capuchin historian is wrong, since the Gurupi region is located to the northwest in Maranhão; the northeast region of Maranhão corresponds today to the micro-regions of Lençóis Maranhenses, Baixo Parnaíba and Chapadinha.

take over the Prelature of Pinheiro. (NEMBRO, 1955, p. 103). The Archbishop of São Luís, Dom Carlos Carmelo, was appointed as Apostolic Administrator of the new circumscription, who in turn asked the Capuchins to remain in their former parish in the region temporarily. In 1946, when the nine Missionaries of the Sacred Heart arrived, Fr. Afonso Maria Ungarelli, MSC (MISSIONÁRIOS..., 1996, p. 11).

According to data recorded in the Anuário Católico do Brasil (CERIS, 1965, p. 673-675), the Prelature *nullius* de Pinheiro, at the end of the Council, covered a total area of 13,709 km², corresponding to 12 municipalities, with a total population of 257,344 inhabitants. There were eight parishes established in the prelature territory. The prelature was attended by 23 priests, 2 lay religious and 54 nuns. The Prelature of Pinheiro also had movements and lay apostolate groups: Apostolate of Prayer, Eucharistic Crusade, International Workers' Circles and Women's Auxiliaries.

2 DOM AFONSO MARIA UNGARELLI, MSC (1897-1988): prosopographic features

Dom Afonso Maria Ungarelli, MSC, was Bishop Prelate *nullius* of Pinheiro from 1948 to 1975 and Apostolic Administrator of the Prelature *nullius* of Cândido Mendes from 1962 to 1965. The only child of Gaetano Ungarelli and Cecilia Bergamini Ungarelli, a wealthy family, was born in Marrara (Ferrara, Italy) on May 2, 1897. He studied at the University of Bologna, graduating and obtaining a doctorate in Chemistry and remaining for some time as Assistant Professor to the Full Professor.

In 1924, Ungarelli entered the novitiate of the Missionaries of the Sacred Heart of Jesus in Marseille, France. He made his religious profession in 1925 and, after completing his philosophical-theological studies at the Pontifical Gregorian University in Rome, he was ordained a priest in 1928. The following year he obtained the degree of Doctor of Theology at the same university. In addition, he was also a Bachelor of Canon Law from the same Pontifical Gregorian University. In the first ten years of his priestly ministry he was director of the Scholasticate of Philosophy and Theology of the Missionaries of the Sacred Heart in Florence, religious superior in the same city and director of the Minor Seminary in Narni.

When the Prelature *nullius* de Pinheiro was created in 1939, the Holy See decided to entrust it to the Congregation of Missionaries of the Sacred Heart. While the General House of the Congregation consulted the superiors of the Italian Province to accept this mission, Fr. Afonso Ungarelli was afraid to take on such a job, since they still did not have enough experience with foreign missions (MISSIONÁRIOS, 1996, p. 68-69). However, Fr. Ungarelli

was the only one of the members of the Provincial Council to be assigned to work in Maranhão when the Prelature was officially handed over to the Missionaries of the Sacred Heart on June 1, 1940.

The Second World War (1939-1945), however, prevented the missionaries from coming to Pinheiro to take up their pastoral work. It was not until 1946 that the first priests came from Italy with Fr. Ungarelli to start the mission in Maranhão lands. Foot. Afonso Maria Ungarelli was appointed Apostolic Administrator of the Prelature by Pope Pius XII on August 18, 1946 (MEIRELES, 1977, p. 323-324).

On November 13, 1948, at last, the prelate Mons. Ungarelli was elevated to episcopal dignity, as titular bishop of Azura, with the episcopal consecration in São Paulo, on March 27, 1949, under the presidency of the now Cardinal D. Carlos Carmelo. After his elevation to the episcopate, he continued, in the words of Archbishop Felipe Condurú Pachêco (1969, p. 615), “to govern his Prelature, with a truly model civic-religious movement”.

In 1955, Bishop Ungarelli managed to send diocesan priests Canadians ¹⁰to help in the parishes of Cururupu, Turiaçu, Peri-Mirim and Bequimão (MISSIONÁRIOS..., 1996, p. 31). When the Prelature *nullius* of Cândido Mendes was created, in October 1961, D. Ungarelli was also appointed Apostolic Administrator of the same, until its first prelate was chosen.

He animated all the dimensions of pastoral work in the Prelature of Pinheiro, remaining in this role until March 1, 1975, when his resignation due to age limit was accepted by Paul VI. He died on May 23, 1988 and his remains, by the will of the then Bishop of Pinheiro, D. Ricardo Paglia, were buried in the Cathedral of the Diocese of Pinheiro.

3 A BISHOP FROM MARANHÃO IN THE VATICAN COUNCIL II

3.1 The Pre-Preparatory Phase (1958-1959) and Archbishop Ungarelli's propositions

After convoking the Council, Pope John XXIII wished to involve the bishops of the whole world in its preparation, as well as the major superiors of religious and theological faculties, through a letter sent by Cardinal Tardini in June 1958, in which he requested the sending *consilia et votes* – advice and proposals, so to speak – on the issues that should be dealt with at the Council (cf. ALBERIGO, 1996, p. 103-104).

¹⁰Two years before Pius XII's appeal in the encyclical *Fidei Donum*, that diocesan priests also become missionaries, remaining incardinated in the diocese of origin.

Among the nine bishops and prelates from Maranhão who could have responded to Cardinal Tardini's request in the preparatory phase, only seven did so. The prelate of Pinheiro, Dom Afonso Ungarelli, presented the largest *votum* of the Maranhão episcopate: almost thirteen pages of text.

Apologizing for having received the letter from the Pre-Preparatory Commission only too late and for having delayed his response, Bishop Ungarelli immediately began to deal with the proposals he wanted to present: institution of catechists and questions related to the sacrament of marriage. Briefly exposing the proposals, the prelate from Pinheiro mentioned two pamphlets that he prepared for a more detailed and in-depth approach to the issues – “De cooperatione laicorum in munere pastorali” and “De convenientia Amendmenti can. 1098, vel potius perficiendi quae can. 1098 statuuntur” – and which were sent together with the letter to the Preparatory Commission.

Throughout his writing, D. Ungarelli presents a portrait of the situation of the missionary territories from his own reality, the Prelature *nullius* de Pinheiro, and draws from it the pastoral consequences: “ in the north of Brazil, as well as in several other regions of Latin America, parishes have an immense size, so the parish priest [...] is not able to carry out his pastoral mission [...]” (ADA I/II,7, p. 288, free translation). Wow).

The Pinheiro prelate continues to present the seriousness of the problem, as he seeks to make the Roman interlocutor understand the situation in all its dimension: “ The Prelature of Pinheiro is the smallest of the Prelatures of Brazil, but it has the same size as the Subalpine Gaul (Piedmont) and Cisalpine Gaul (Lombardy) together ” (ADA I/II,7, p. 288, our free translation).

Pastoral action in the Prelature is carried out only under the style defined by the prelate as “walking missions” or “ commonly known as 'disobrigas', which is the annual visit that the Priest makes so that the faithful fulfill their *religious obligations* : Confession and Communion at least once a year” (ADA I/II,7, p. 287; emphasis added by the author).

The consequences of the deficient religious assistance in the vast prelate are many: children in rural areas do not receive any catechesis; many who call themselves Christians do not even know how to say the “Our Father” and the “Hail Mary”; public prayer, performed only when Holy Mass is celebrated on some Sunday or feast day, fell into disuse; the sacraments, apart from Baptism, are all neglected; many, because of this, fall into heresy for listening to Protestant pastors and spiritist leaders; there is a serious danger of perversion on the part of the Christian people, due to the lack of spiritual assistance, which leaves them like sheep without a shepherd at the mercy of ravenous wolves (cf. ADA I/II,7, p. 287-288).

As a solution, Archbishop Ungarelli proposes that some well-prepared lay people be entrusted with responsibilities for the care of souls that do not require the use of orders, with the aim of helping priests and favoring the *bonum animarum* (good of souls) of the faithful. The catechists were to be trained for three years in a “Diocesan Institute for Cooperating Catechists”, where they would study the Sacred Scriptures and catechesis in a particular way.

D. Ungarelli then began to suggest concrete ways of inserting his entire proposal into the current canonical *corpus*, proposing amendments to Part III (*De laicis*) of Book II (*De personis*) of the 1917 Code, presenting four canons to be inserted and that legally summarize the suggestions presented in the *votum*.

In another booklet that he presented to the Preparatory Commission, Bishop Ungarelli demonstrates how the absence of priests in mission lands and the negligence of the faithful towards the sacraments – including marriage – is a cause of serious scandals for society.

The canon in question deals with the so-called extraordinary form of marriage ¹¹. Archbishop Ungarelli sees in the extraordinary form of Matrimony a possibility of favoring access to the sacrament in remote parishes and communities and he doesn't care to prove that from the non-application and ignorance of this canonical device several harmful consequences arise.

Bishop Ungarelli's proposal for the problem, in short, is to train cooperating catechists to educate the people about can. 1098 and its application and name them as qualified witnesses, being able to request and receive the consent that the bride and groom give to each other. To this end, once again, Pinheiro's antistite directly suggests modifications to the text of the Code of Canon Law, with a view to applying his suggestions in the chapters dealing with Marriages (ADA I/II,7, p. 297-298).

3.2 Preparatory Phase (1960-1962): Bishop Ungarelli in the Commission for the Discipline of the Sacraments

The Preparatory phase of Vatican II began with the publication of the *Motu Proprio Superno Dei Nutu*, on June 5, 1960. In this pontifical document the principles of action of each of the various preparatory commissions were given. The commissions would be composed “of

¹¹When the bride and groom are in danger of death or when the ecclesiastical assistant able to receive the consent of the bride and groom is absent and this absence is foreseen with moral certainty that it will last for a month, and the bride and groom cannot turn to the religious minister without serious inconvenience, the marriage contracted by the two spouses before two witnesses is valid and lawful.

Cardinals, Bishops and Ecclesiastics, distinguished by virtue and doctrine, both from the secular clergy and from the regular clergy, chosen from different parts of the world” (JOÃO XXIII, 1962, p. 56).

Archbishop Ungarelli was chosen as a consultor to the Commission for the Discipline of the Sacraments (cf. BEOZZO, 2005, p. 128) and his appointment was made public in the “Acta Apostolicae Sedis” of 25 October of the same year (cf. AAS 52, 1960, p. 846).

The prelate and canonist from Maranhão was thus summoned to offer his contribution to the Council in the area in which his *votum* was *precisely concentrated*, which was well articulated and based on pastoral experience. The work of the various pre-conciliar commissions and, in particular, the role of Bishop Ungarelli in the Commission for the Discipline of the Sacraments, remains open for future research.

3.3 Sessions of the Second Vatican Council (1962-1965): Bishop Ungarelli in the Conciliar Aula and in the *Missionibus Commission*

The Council, prepared by commissions formed by members of the Roman Curia assisted by bishops and theologians from various countries of the world, was conceived as a quick assembly for the approval of about 70 schemes, drawn up from the synthesis of the proposals of the bishops and the Curia itself. .

However, already in the first General Congregation of the First Session of the Council, on October 13, 1962, it was noticed that the atmosphere was different among the Council Fathers: at the suggestion of Cardinal Liénart, with the support of Cardinal Frings, who spoke on behalf of also by Cardinals Döpfner and König (RICCARDI, 2000, p. 43), the election of the conciliar commissions was postponed, so that the Episcopal Conferences – that new ecclesial body that emerged shortly before Vatican II and there demonstrated its functionality – would have time to organize candidate lists.

Although the National Conference of Bishops of Brazil did not prepare any list of candidates (RICCARDI, 2000, p. 52), among those elected to the conciliar commissions there was also a Maranhão: Dom Afonso Maria Ungarelli, prelate *nullius* de Pinheiro, who had already participated from the Preparatory Commission on the Discipline of the Sacraments was elected to another commission, that of Missions.

The Council had the Liturgy as its first topic of debate, starting with the fourth General Congregation, on October 22, 1962. On the first day of debates, some personalities who would gain prominence in the Council Hall, such as Cardinals Frings, Lercaro, Montini and Spellman.

Along with these great names, there is that of Dom Ungarelli, with the nineteenth oral intervention of the day. In his intervention – which lasted more than 10 minutes and had to be interrupted – the prelate questioned the excessive importance given by the *schema* to the Latin rite in reference to other expressions of the Catholic Church and the clinging of the text to the need to use the language Latin in liturgy everywhere:

However, this postulate, that is, that the Latin language should be used throughout the world, we do not see it agree with the purposes of the sacred Liturgy for these reasons: *First reason* : In this way the postulate seems to prevent the union of the Churches. [...] However, if the entire Western Liturgy must observe the use of the Latin language (p. 167, n. 24, lin. 10-11), an unnecessary impediment to conciliation with the separated Brothers remains, for example with the Protestants, who use the vernacular language, and for whom it is perhaps easier to enter the Catholic Church, removing the impediment of language... [...] (AS I/1, p. 336; emphasis added by the author, our free translation).

The second reason presented by Archbishop Ungarelli, on the other hand, is based on the missionary nature of the Church: “ The postulate of which we have been speaking seems even more to hinder the evangelization of the infidels, to whom Christ the Lord compels us all ” (AS I/1, p. 337, our free translation).

The third reason pointed out by Bishop Ungarelli is related to vocations, given the great need due to the lack of priests: “ the formation of those called to the priestly ministry will become easier, which is a matter of great importance at this moment ” (AS I/ 1, p. 337, our free translation).

Bishop Ungarelli goes even further, proposing the creation of new rites, since they all enjoy the same honor and dignity for the Church and in the past it was possible to have a multiplicity of them. D. Ungarelli argues: “ But if in antiquity it seemed appropriate to institute different rites [...], why is it not appropriate today to institute new rites, if in many places the situation corresponds more or less to ancient times? ” (AS I/1, p. 338, our free translation).

A few days later, Archbishop Ungarelli presented a new intervention, this time in writing, with the same content as the one read in the fourth General Congregation, adding the request that the *schema* be modified so as to say that the document and its norms only concerned the Roman rite and not to all the liturgical traditions of the Church (AS I/1, p. 661). 29 bishops were associated with it, including D. Antonio Batista Fragoso, then auxiliary bishop of São Luís.

The Second Session of the Council, led by Paul VI, had five interventions by Council Fathers from Maranhão: one by D. Condurú Pachêco and four by D. Marelím, all delivered in

writing. It should be noted the absence of contributions from Archbishop Ungarelli, certainly absorbed in the enormous work of preparing the scheme on the Church's missionary activity.

The new air of 1964 brought hope to the Third Session of Vatican II: perhaps this was the last period. This was how Paul VI and many Council Fathers thought, wishing that they could soon return definitively to their diocesan sees to deal with the needs of their faithful (KOMONCHAK, 2007, p. 17). The Third Session of Vatican II therefore had a vast program, which aimed to account for all the remaining schemes. Toward the end of this Third Session, we have Bishop Ungarelli's intervention on the scheme "De activitate missionali Ecclesiae" (On the Church's missionary activity). D. Ungarelli's intervention makes several claims:

1. Determine the theology of mission: a) From the Sacred Scriptures and the testimonies of the Holy Fathers (Bea, Frings, Zoghbi); b) From the perennial and urgent need of the missionary office (Suenens, Bea, Alfrink); c) in relation to so-called ecumenism and religious freedom.
2. Review the juridical notion of mission, if the meaning that prevails until now, or if German missionary activity does not correspond to the condition (Fulton Sheen, Riobé, Grotti).
3. Develop the consequences of collegiality, such as central bodies for the direction of missionary activity (Léger, Frings) or the offices and works of particular Churches (Frings, Carretto).
4. Define the dispositions of evangelization in the face of the so-called "third world".
5. Other interventions on themes foreshadowed for the new text, which seems better to comment on: a) adaptation (Léger, Rugambwa, Doi, Lokuang); b) lay people and catechumens (Suenens); c) relations between missionary bishops and missionary institutes (Grotti); d) Catholic schools in the missions (Nguyen Van Thuan and Schneider in the discussion "about Catholic schools"). (AS III/6, p. 633, our free translation).

Bishop Ungarelli's intervention is like a synthetic collection of the contributions of the various Council Fathers over the three days of discussion of the scheme, which was widely criticized - they referred to it as "bones without flesh", for the total disconnection from the "Of Ecclesia".

In the Fourth Session, the last of the Second Vatican Council, there were still a large number of schemes to be discussed and approved. The interventions of the bishops of Maranhão, in spite of that, decreased a lot. Symptomatically, only Dom Marelim and Dom Ungarelli spoke about the schemes in 1965 – almost as representatives of opposing tendencies in the Council.

Archbishop Ungarelli's intervention (cf. AS IV/4, p. 652-655), aimed at the debate on the scheme "De activitate missionali ecclesiae", dealt mainly with the concept of mission (dynamic or territorial) and its application in different realities, such as, for example, the Amazon, and on the creation of a central body for the missions.

On the territoriality of the mission, Archbishop Ungarelli spoke for countless prelates of particular churches where the hierarchy and the clergy are not sufficiently established, where ecclesial structures are still precarious and which, however, are not part of the so-called “mission territories”. The questions raised by Bishop Ungarelli were echoed by the Conciliar Commission on Missions and were recorded in a note of the *Ad Gentes Decree* on the Church's missionary activity (n. 6, note 37):

This notion of missionary activity, as can be seen, also includes, in terms of substance, those regions of Latin America in which neither a proper hierarchy, nor maturity of the Christian life, nor sufficient preaching of the Gospel are yet given. Whether, however, these territories are in fact regarded by the Holy See as missionaries does not depend on the Council: that is why, with regard to the connection between the notion of missionary activity and certain territories, it is very intentionally said that this activity is carried out “generally” (plerumque) in certain territories recognized as such by the Holy See. (DOCUMENTS, 2012, p. 441-442).

In fact, Bishop Ungarelli had presented data in his intervention on the size of the Amazon area, with a multitude of baptized people and very few clergy (AS IV/4, p. 653-654). In his argument, he pointed out that there was no reason to reduce the concept of mission to preaching the Gospel *in partibus infidelium*, that is, among non-believers.

CONCLUSION

In the research presented here, we can identify the fruits of Dom Afonso Maria Ungarelli's performance at the Second Vatican Council. The figure of this council priest emerges as a pastor with his eyes on the future, his feet on the ground and his voice raised to cry out. A far-sighted, forward looking look that was able to concretely suggest the participation of lay people in pastoral ministry even before the conciliar debates began. Deep roots in the local reality, which led him to propose ways to overcome the difficulties of pastoral care and also, on the other hand, to question the very formulation of the concept of mission in the conciliar debates. A voice raised among the great names of the Church to defend their ideas already in the first General Congregation, and which fought for the recognition of the missionary reality of its prelature and many others in Latin America.

The voice of Archbishop Ungarelli, which was heard in the Vatican Basilica and in the Commission *De Missionibus*, still resounds today in the Decree on the missionary activity of the *Ad Gentes Church*, n. 6, note 37. A simple footnote, but which reflects the thought and

experience of a missionary who, dedicated to the people entrusted to him and aware of their needs, also knew how to recognize their particularities in the evangelization process.

The commitment of Archbishop Ungarelli, later, in the reflections of the episcopate of Maranhão and in the joint pastoral planning to “receive” and implement the Second Vatican Council in his Diocese, also manifests his commitment as Father Conciliar to enforce what the bishops of all the world discussed, decided and declared in the Conciliar Class. Approaching the sixty years of the beginning of Vatican II, looking at the trajectory and pastoral options of the Maranhão Council Fathers - among which Dom Ungarelli, in Pinheiro - will allow a better understanding of the path taken by the Church in Maranhão since then and, also, check what still needs to be done to implement the Council's decisions today.

REFERENCES

ACTA APOSTOLICÆ SEDIS: commentarium officiale. Romæ: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, Annus XXXII, Series II, Vol. VII, 1940. Available at: <http://www.vatican.va/archive/aas/index_po.htm>. Accessed on: 04 Feb. 2022. [AAS 32, 1940].

_____ Romæ: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, Annus LII, Series III, Vol. II, 1960. Available at: <http://www.vatican.va/archive/aas/index_en.htm>. Accessed on: 04 Feb. 2022. [AAS 52, 1960].

ACTA ET DOCUMENTA VATICAN OECUMENICO CONCILIO II APPARANDO. Volumen II: Consilia et vote Episcoporum ac Praelatorum. Pars VII: America meridionalis – Oceania (under secret). Rome: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, 1961. [ADA I/II,7]

ACTA SYNODALIA SACROSANCTI CONCILII OECUMENICI VATICANI II. Volume I: Periodus prima. Pars I: Session publishes I. Congregationes generales I-IX. Rome: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, 1970. [AS I/1]

_____ Volume III: Periodus tertia. Pars VI: Congregationes generales CXII-CXVIII. Rome: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, 1975. [AS III/6]

_____ Volume IV: Periodus Fourth. Pars IV: Congregationes generales CXLVI-CL. Rome: Typis Polyglottis Vaticanis, 1977. [AS IV/4]

ALBERIGO, Giuseppe (right). **History of the Second Vatican Council**. vol. 1: Catholicism towards the new era: the proclamation and preparation of Vatican II (January 1959 to October 1962). Petrópolis: Voices, 1996.

_____ **History of the Second Vatican Council**. vol. 2: The formation of the conciliar conscience: the first period and the first intersection (October 1962 to September 1963). Petrópolis: Voices, 2000.

_____ **History of the Second Vatican Council** . vol. 4: La Iglesia como comunión: The third period and the third intersesión (Sept. 1964-Sept. 1965). Salamanca: Sígueme, 2007. (El peso de los días, 55)

BEOZZO, José Oscar (org.). **The Church of Brazil in the Second Vatican Council: 1959-1965**. Sao Paulo, Paulinas, 2005.

CENTER FOR RELIGIOUS STATISTICS AND SOCIAL RESEARCH – CERIS. **Catholic Yearbook of Brazil 1965** . Rio de Janeiro: Graphic Service of the IBGE Foundation, 1966.

DOCUMENTS OF THE II VATICAN COUNCIL (1962-1965). 6. reprint Sao Paulo: Paulus, 2012.

JOHN XXIII. Motu Proprio “Superno Dei Nutu”. In: KLOPPENBURG, Boaventura. **Second Vatican Council** . vol. I: Pre-reconciliation documentary. Petrópolis: Vozes, 1962. p. 55-57.

KOMONCHAK, Joseph. “There was an ecclesiology of communication”. In: ALBERIGO, Giuseppe. (right). **History of the Second Vatican Council** . vol. 4: La Iglesia como comunión: The third period and the third intersesión (Sept. 1964-Sept. 1965). Salamanca: Sígueme, 2007. (El peso de los días, 55). P. 16-97.

KLOPPENBURG, Boaventura. **Second Vatican Council** . vol. I: Pre-reconciliation documentary. Petrópolis: Vozes, 1962.

MACHADO, Laersio da Silva. **The Bishops of Maranhão at the Second Vatican Ecumenical Council: votes , participation and interventions of the Council Fathers**. Advisor: Humberto Guidotti. 2012. 290 f. Monograph (Bachelor of Theology) – Institute of Higher Studies of Maranhão, São Luís, 2012.

MARQUES, Cesar Augusto. **Historical-Geographic Dictionary of the Province of Maranhão** . 3.ed. Notes and textual verification by Jomar Moraes. São Luís: AML Editions, 2008.

MEIRELES, Mario Martins. **History of the Archdiocese of São Luís do Maranhão: in the tercentenary of the creation of the diocese**. São Luís: University of Maranhão/SIOGE, 1977.

MISSIONARIES OF THE SACRED HEART OF JESUS. **50 years in Pinheiro and for Pinheiro** . [Y/L]: [Y/E], 1996.

NEMBRO, Methodius of. **São José de Grajaú, first Prelature of Maranhão** . Fortaleza: The Voice of San Francisco, 1955.

PACÊCO, Felipe Benício Condurú (Sunday). **Ecclesiastical history of Maranhão** . São Luís: SENEC/Department of Culture, 1969. (Collection “César Marques”, 1).

RICARDI, Andrea. “The tumultuous opening of work”. In: In: ALBERIGO, Giuseppe. (right). **History of the Second Vatican Council**. vol. 2: The formation of the conciliar conscience: the first period and the first intersection (October 1962 to September 1963). Petrópolis: Vozes, 2000. p. 21-76.